

HOW TO LEARN A NEW FOREIGN LANGUAGE EASY AND FAST

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Annotation: You can learn about how to learn the foreign language faster and easier, the easy ways of effective learning and lots of advice for new learners. It includes some steps which give feedback for learning and teaching easy and effective.

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Do you want to learn a new language for yourself?

Maybe you need to learn a language so you can speak it on an upcoming trip;

Or so you can take on a new job;

Or maybe you want to read your lovely novel on its source language;

Whatever your reason for learning a new language, you can probably agree it'd be ideal to learn it easy and fast. Yet the idea of learning a language, especially when you're learning it from scratch, seems anything but fast: You'll have to learn a new grammar, memorize vocabulary words, practice speaking... But learning a new language doesn't need to be a slow or tedious process. Although nothing can replace the hard work and effort it requires, you can absolutely learn a new foreign language fast if you follow the right strategy and dedicate yourself to the process. According to the following steps, you learn about how to learn the new language easy and faster than you ever imagined!

Set language-learning goals.

The first step to learning a new language fast is to set goals for what you want to achieve. When you think about it, this makes a lot of sense. If you don't set goals, how can you know what you want to achieve and measure whether you have achieved it? When faced with the idea of learning a new language, most of us feel overwhelmed. There are so many words to learn and so many different ways to study. Setting goals narrows your focus so you can stop worrying about the details and get down to business.

Research shows that people who set the right kind of goals are more likely to achieve success.

Use these guidelines to get the most from your goals:

Focus on specific, tangible outcomes. Set detailed goals, and focus on what you plan to learn rather than how much time you plan to study. An example of a

good goal might be, “This week I’m going to learn 30 English vocabulary words related to School life.”

Set short-term goals. It’s good to have an ultimate goal – the thing you eventually hope to achieve. But long – term goals are too overwhelming to motivate you on an everyday basis. Break down your ultimate goal into smaller bits, and set smaller goals for each week or month.

Write down your goals. Writing down goals helps you commit to them. Post your goals in a prominent place, like your mirror or the home screen of your smartphone.

Learn the “right” words.

Languages are made up of a shocking number of words. English, for example, has between 600,000 and 1 million words. Luckily, you don’t need to learn anywhere near that many words to be proficient in a language. Consider this: the top 100 words make up about 50 percent of English language texts, and the top 1,000 words make up about 90 percent!

Study smart.

When learning your words, you’ll learn faster by using the very best study techniques. For example, one of the best ways to learn vocabulary words is to use flashcards. Flashcards help you focus on individual words and allow you to test yourself, which helps you memorize new information.

When you learn with flashcards, follow these tips to learn fast:

Try out electronic flashcards. Paper flashcards work just as well as they ever did, but electronic flashcard programs provide some great benefits. By using electronic flashcards, you can easily carry large stacks on your smartphone or tablet, and you can take advantage of flashcards that other people have created and made public. These programs also automatically change the order of cards and use spaced repetition to gradually increase the amount of time between repetitions of a flashcard. Both of these techniques help you learn faster and better.

Make sure to guess the meaning of a word before turning over the card. Flashcards work best when you use them to test your memory, so don’t be too quick to flip the cards over. Even if you don’t know a word, make a guess.

Visualize and vocalize. Visualize the word you’re learning, imagine the image of what it represents and say the new word aloud. This helps you connect the concepts and can improve memorization. Use the word in your native language. When you’re learning a new language, it can be hard to practice words in context because you haven’t yet mastered enough vocabulary to make complex sentences.

To get around this, simply use the word in your native language. For example, if you're learning the English word house (uy), you could say, "Men hozir housega ketayapman."

Start using the language all day, every day.

As a beginner, it can seem overwhelming to try to use the language all day, but it's not as difficult as it seems. There are many easy and even fun ways to make the language a part of your regular life.

First, make use of every moment you have to learn new words. Take flashcards with you, and study them during your train or bus commute or when you're waiting to meet a friend. When you start to feel tired, switch from active learning to passive learning by doing what you would normally do in your native language in your target language. Try watching a video or TV show, or streaming radio broadcasts in your target language.

Test yourself

Knowing that you plan to take a test is a great way to motivate yourself to learn faster. Try to regularly test yourself in little ways. If you're learning from a textbook, take practice tests or complete the exercises at the end of each chapter. You can also play online games or take online tests. Planning to take a standardized test several months to a year after you begin learning a new language can also keep you motivated, and having the results can help you "prove" your language level to potential employers, schools or even just yourself. Some languages also have a standardized test specific to that language, such as the JLPT for Japanese or the IELTS for English. Ask teachers or professionals who know the language what tests they recommend.

Have fun

We tend to learn best when we're enjoying ourselves, so don't forget to make language learning fun. Playing games is a great way to have fun while learning. Games take advantage of our natural competitiveness and can help us practice language skills even when we feel tired. You can also focus your learning on things that you find interesting, like a favorite hobby. If you're learning English and fascinated by English politics, learn words used to describe political processes, and immerse yourself in articles about political issues, videos of political debates and talk shows about current events. Finally, make friends who speak your target language or are interested in learning it. Languages aren't meant to be learned in a vacuum! Real-life social events and conversations are what make language learning fun and worthwhile. Make a point of talking to people and learning more about their lives and cultures. You might be surprised

at how excited they are to share information with you, and how quickly you make lasting friendships in the process.

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